

Table 1; Summary of median immune cell fractions estimated using EPIC deconvolution in normal vs. tumor samples across 48 canine mammary tissues. Wilcoxon test p-values indicate the significance of difference in abundance for each immune cell type

Cell Type	Normal	Tumor	p-value
Bcells	0.116	0.198	0.0840
CAFs	0.0272	0.0168	0.518
CD4 ⁺ T cells	0.0312	0.150	0.0266
CD8 ⁺ T cells	0.0819	0.161	0.0607
Endothelial	0.240	0.123	0.0803
Macrophages	0.0193	0.0134	0.782
NK cells	0.275	0.197	0.164
otherCells	0.209	0.140	0.170